

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURES

Combining molecular data sets with strongly heterogeneous taxon coverage enlightens the peculiar biogeographic history of Stoneflies (Insecta: Plecoptera)

Harald Letsch^{1,2,*}, Sabrina Simon³, Paul B. Frandsen^{4,5}, Shanlin Liu⁶, Ryuichiro Machida⁷, Christoph Mayer⁸, Bernhard Misof⁸, Oliver Niehuis⁹, Xin Zhou⁶, Benjamin Wipfler^{8,*}

Fig. S1: Results of the super tree reconstruction analyses of the transcriptomic single gene tree data sets using “Matrix representation with Parsimony” (MRP). a) 278 gene trees data set, b) 389 gene trees data set, c) 1764 gene trees data set, d) 2997 gene trees data set.

Fig. S2: Results of the super tree reconstruction analyses of the transcriptomic single gene tree data sets using FastRFS. a) 278 gene trees data set, b) 389 gene trees data set, c) 1764 gene trees data set, d) 2997 gene trees data set.

Fig. S3: Results of the ML tree reconstruction analyses of the concatenated transcriptomic data sets. a) 278 genes data set, b) 389 genes data set, c) 1764 genes data set, d) 2997 genes data set.

Fig. S4: Heat maps showing the results from pairwise comparison of species in the concatenated transcriptomic data sets using Bowker's test of symmetry. White boxes with p-values > 0.05 indicate that the corresponding species pair does not violate the assumption of global stationary, reversibility, and homogeneity (SRH conditions). a) 278 genes data set, b) 389 genes data set, c) 1764 genes data set, d) 2997 genes data set.

Fig. S5: Results of the unconstrained best ML tree reconstruction analyses in IQ-TREE of the concatenated Sanger sequence data set.

Fig. S6: Results of the BEAST Bayesian Inference analyses, showing the relationships and divergence times of stoneflies.

Fig. S7: Results of net diversification rate over time estimations in Systellognatha and Euholognatha. Rates of the individual (super-)families were extracted by the rate-through-time approach with BAMMtools. Grey polygon denotes the 10% through 90% Bayesian credible regions on the distribution of rates as calculated in BAMM.

Fig. S1a

Fig. S1b

Fig. S1c

Fig. S1d

Fig. S2a

Fig. S2b

Fig. S2c

Fig. S2d

Fig. S3a

Fig. S3b

Fig. S3c

Fig. S3d

Fig. S4a

Fig. S4b

Fig. S4c

Fig. S4d

- Diamphipnoidae
- Eustheniidae
- Stenoperlinae
- “Austroperlidae”
- “Leptoperlinae”
- “Gripopteryginae”
- “Dinotoperlinae”
- Gripopterygidae
- “Antarctoperlinae”
- “Zelandoperlinae”
- Styloperlidae
- Peltopteridae
- Peltopterinae
- Pteronarcyidae
- Kathroperla*
- Acroneuriinae
- Perlidae
- Perlinae
- “Chloroperlinae”
- Paraperlinae
- Chloroperlidae
- “Chloroperlinae”
- “Perlodinae”
- “Isoperlinae”
- Perlodidae
- “Nemourinae”
- “Amphinemurinae”
- Nemouridae
- Notonemouridae
- Euniopterygidae
- Leuctridae
- Leuctrinae
- Scopuridae
- Taeniopterygidae
- Brachypterainae
- Taeniopteryginae
- Megaleuctridae
- Megaleuctra, *Alcaid*
- Megaleuctra, *eligmata*
- Capniidae

Antarctoperlaria

Systellognatha

Euniopterygidae

Fig. S6

Diamphipnoidea

Eustheniidae

"Austroperlidae"

Griopterygidae

Styloperlidae

Peltoperlidae

Pteronarcyidae

Kathroperla

Perlidae

Chloroperlidae

Perlodidae

Nemouridae

Notonemouridae

Leuctridae

Scopuridae

Taeniopterygidae

Megaleuctridae

Capniidae

Eustheniinae

Stenoperlinae

"Leptoperlinae"

"Griopteryginae"

"Dinotoperlinae"

"Antarctoperlinae"

"Zelandoperlinae"

Peltoperlinae

Acroneuriinae

Perlinae

"Chloroperlinae"

Paraperlinae

"Chloroperlinae"

"Perlodinae"

"Isoperlinae"

"Nemourinae"

"Amphinemurinae"

Leuctrinae

Taeniopteryginae

Brachypterinae

Antarctoperlaria

Systellognatha

Euholognatha

50.0

200

100

0

Fig. S7

